

Supplementary Reference Document for the paper

“A Framework for the Profitable Integration of Distributed Ledger Technologies in Enterprise Networks”

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Abstract:

This Supplementary Reference Document provides the detailed list of references for the challenges and benefits identified in the main paper titled "A Framework for the Profitable Integration of Distributed Ledger Technologies in Enterprise Networks." The outcomes in this document are derived from the literature review conducted as part of the paper, focusing on the key challenges and benefits of integrating Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) in enterprise networks. This extended reference list supports the claims made in the challenges and benefits tables and offers an additional resource for readers to explore the underlying literature.

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